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One pot-synthesis of poly(lactic acid-g-vinyl alcohol)

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Introduction: Optimal Controlled drug delivery systems should be able to release the drug in a controlled manner, biocompatible, inert, and capable of achieving a high drug loading (1-5). Among the materials used in the controlled release, polyesters such as polylactic acid (PLA) stands out because of its properties and due to the FDA approval for human use (6-10). However, because of its low polarity, the interaction between this polymer and some drugs is impaired. To perform a copolymerization with more hydrophilic polymers such as polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is an alternative. By grafting PVA to PLA, a new amphiphilic copolymer is formed, which allows the insertion of different pharmaceutical molecules.

Methods: In this work, PLA was synthesized from lactic acid using sulfuric acid as catalyst. For PVA grafting, PLA was previously modified with maleic anhydride, and PVA grafting was done from this modified polymer. The PLA molar mass was determined via Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC), Hydrogen Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (¹H-NMR) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC).

Results & Discussions: The molar mass of synthesized PLA was measured by SEC. Number Average Molecular Weight (M_n) was 1807 and Weight Average Molecular Weight (M_w) was 3385 with a polydispersion of 1.87. This value is within the desirable range for application in controlled drug delivery systems. For the confirmation of PLA modification and PVA grafting, the Hydrogen Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (¹H-NMR) was used. The PLA peaks around 5 ppm corresponding to CH groups and around 1.6 ppm corresponding to CH₃ groups. The modification of PLA with maleic anhydride was confirmed by the appearance of a peak around 3.7 ppm corresponding to the CH₂ group present in the inserted compound molecule, maintaining the PLA peaks. The graftization could also be confirmed by the appearance of PVA peaks linked to the PLA structure. Modification with maleic anhydride and grafting with PVA were also evaluated by DSC. It could be observed that the crystallization peak for pure PLA is narrower than for PLAM and PLA-g-PVA, indicating the formation of crystals with more homogeneous size distribution. The crystallization peak of pure PLA is narrower due to the formation of crystals with greater perfection and smaller size distribution.

Conclusions: The PLA-g-PVA polymer was successfully synthesized and characterized by SEC, H-NMR and DSC. This new amphiphilic polymer matrix is a good alternative for drug delivery, since it is possible to insert drugs with different polarities.

Key words: PLA, PVA, drug delivery, synthesis.

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